

INDICATIVE METHODS OF HISTORY TEACHING

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Abstract. Teaching method when you say education in the process teacher and of students known to the goal to reach directed together activity methods is understood. Otherwise by doing in other words, teaching both methods of activity, that is teacher by students knowledge, skill and skills with arming, moral in terms of education in them scientific worldview formation and students by that's it mean caught scientific knowledge, skill and qualifications appropriation in the activity applied methods own into takes

Key words Uzbekistan, history, method, education, training, method.

History whole the world in their schools centuries during read bride is a science. This is the past is learning and this to us Where that we came and today's to the day how that we have achieved to understand help will give. in Uzbekistan history science study " History called " teaching ". and teachers to the students the past meaningful and interesting way to learn help giving one how much different of methods they use History in education the most wide spread out of methods one from textbooks is to use. Textbooks the past events thoroughness with studied and documented historian and pedagogues by written Later on this books to the students historical events, people and civilizations about complete information to give for in class is used. Textbooks students for valuable source is because they are information in order and understandable in the format present is enough

Of teachers history science in teaching who uses again one method this primary from sources is to use. Primary sources original documents or being studied period are artifacts. To these letters, diaries, photographs, newspapers and the government records enters Primary sources study through students historical events about directly to the imagination have to be and critical thinking abilities development can Teachers history lessons improve for textbooks and main from sources they also use multimedia resources. These are videos, movies, audio recordings and interactive websites own into take can Multimedia resources students for history to revive help will give and the subject more interesting and more convenient does History in education more and more becoming popular going innovative of methods one simulation and role from the games is to use. This events of students historical persons roles own responsibilities that they get and main events staging own into takes This

practical approach to students to history diving and historical of individuals motives and decisions deeper to understand enable will give.

Excursions history science of teaching again one efficient method is considered Museums, historical places and cultural monuments pilgrimage to do through students historical events happen has been places directly to see can Field trips students for history to revive help will give and the subject more sure and real does This traditional of methods except teachers history in teaching they also use technology. Online resources, virtual tours and digital archives to students many data and resources finger at the tip present reach can Technology history students for interactive and interesting to do help will give. Historical debate and discussions history in education applied again one important is a method. To the students historical to events differently views present reach and them the evidence analysis to do and to evaluate encourage through teachers in students critical thinking skills to develop and the past about thin the concept to develop help will give.

Teachers history in teaching who uses final of methods one to the project based on is education. Project based on in education students extended, practical projects on it works while of them known one historical topic according to information research analysis to do and synthesis requires doing. This is the method in students research and presentation skills to develop help gives, that's it with together historical events deeper to understand achieves History to people social and cultural changes to understand help giving is an important science, it is collective to himself characteristic in formation important role plays To this end history science efficient teach of students in the past of events importance and their present to the day effect in understanding important importance occupation is enough in Uzbekistan history science in teaching " History of teaching should be shown methods " name with famous was different methods is used. These are methods the students attraction to do and their to learn facilitate for innovative and interactive approaches own into takes This essay history in education of teaching efficient methods of use importance, " History of teaching should be shown principles of methods and their students to understand and critical thinking ability effect learns

History of teaching main purpose not only the past events about knowledge give maybe in students critical thinking skills from forming consists of Study efficient methods use of students historical events analysis do, primary sources comment, past and present time in the middle connection ability

increase enable will give. History Teaching Must show Methods active study and of students activity emphasizing the students critical to thinking and historical concepts deeper to understand encourages. " History of teaching should be shown methods". main principles one students study to the process attraction to do for interactive and practical from training use is considered Simulations, role-playing game exercises and group discussions own into received without, teachers students active participation to do and peers with cooperation to do encouraging deep learning environment to create can This approach not only history more closer and interesting does, maybe to students important communication and in the team work skills to develop help will give. History Teaching Must show Methods of again one important aspect history in education of technology integration. Multimedia resources, digital archives and online data bases used without teachers to students historical sources and of information wide to the circle access provide can Not only that of students research skills increases, perhaps to them different point of view glances learning and historical events more complete to understand enable will give. Interactive events and technology from integration except, History Teaching Must show Methods historical events contextualization and of students vital experiences with connection importance emphasizes. Past events current problems and social trends with tie up through teachers to students modern society in formation of history importance to understand help to give can This approach historical events effect deeper to understand help will give and students around the world critical to evaluate encourages. In addition, " History of teaching Instructable Methods history in education primary sources and original from documents to use priority importance is given Letters, diaries, photographs and artifacts such as primary sources analysis to do through students critical thinking abilities development and historical to events directly views can Such approach not only of students research and analytical skills increases, perhaps historical stories more deeper to understand help will give.

From this except, History Teaching Must show Methods in students historical sympathy the feeling bring up importance emphasizes. Students in the past of individuals prospects and experiences seeing to exit encourage through teachers to the students history more empathic and inclusive to understand to develop help to give can This approach cultural sensitivity promote does and students history during human of experiences to recognize diversity encourages. From this besides, " History Teaching Must show Methods " in students critical thinking and analytical skills to develop priority

importance will give. Read the students complicated historical inquiries, discussions and to discussions attraction to do through teachers in students the evidence evaluation, relations installation and justified evidence Create ability development can This approach not only students academic to success prepares, perhaps them informed citizenship and for life education get for important skills with equips

From this except, History Teaching Instructable Methods historical the mind promote to do and cultural inheritance preserve importance emphasizes. Read the students historical places, monuments and of artifacts importance showing to training attraction reach through teachers their own cultural to his heritage relatively pride and pride feelings wake up can This approach the past with deeper to connect strengthens and students historical memory storage and promote in doing active participation to do encourages. Summary by doing to say if we are, of teaching efficient methods students interesting, critical thinking skills formation, the past deeper perception to do help through history in education solution doer place holds

Summary by doing to say in Uzbekistan history science in teaching teachers by applied different methods there is. Teachers textbooks, basic resources, multimedia resources, simulations, excursions, technology, debates and project based on of education from the combination used without in students the past in every way to understand help will give and to history for life love wakes up. History only the date and the facts from memorization consists of it's not ; this humanity of experience complexities and our past today's our day how formed and our future how in formation continue that it will to understand directed.

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